

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ *Echinococcus granulosus* _Adult parasite detection in domestic dogs

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of the adult <i>E. granulosus</i> parasite in domestic dogs.
2	Surveillance aim	Case finding for elimination of the parasite from the host and eradication programs. If it is possible to monitor veterinary records, then it would be possible to use them to identify the introduction of the pathogen into new geographic areas, or to identify signals for change in disease patterns and temporal trends. Because the samples are biased, sample prevalence (the proportion of the sample that tested positive) must be interpreted with caution. Therefore, care must be taken when interpreting signals based on changing sample prevalence, and all signals should be verified with disease investigations or other studies.
3	Target species and group	Domestic dogs (definitive hosts).
4	Target sector / production type	Domestic dogs.
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country.
6	Age group	All.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Veterinary clinics.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round.
9	Sampling matrix	Faeces.
10	Type of disease indicators	None in definitive hosts.
11	Sampling unit	Animal.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	When dogs are vaccinated/micro-chipped, and when dogs enter the country. High-risk groups are dogs living with sheep, such as guardian dogs, sheep herding dogs and dogs that are pets on sheep farms.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	The sedimentation and flotation technique of faecal samples allows detecting taeniid eggs and worm fragments, followed by the differentiation of the different taeniid parasites by PCR.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component contributes to case detection and possibly allows comparing relative risks across geographical areas, but it has to be noted that this is a biased (non-probability based) sample of the population (convenience sampling) and therefore cannot be used directly for estimating the system sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Ticks found on dogs at the time of examination could be tested for tick borne pathogens such as <i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> .
18	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Romig, T., Dinkel, A., & Mackenstedt, U. (2006). The present situation of echinococcosis in Europe. <i>Parasitology international</i>, 55, S187-S191. 2) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2021-zoonoses-report 3) Otero-Abad B., Torgerson P.R.A (2013) Systematic Review of the Epidemiology of Echinococcosis in Domestic and Wild Animals <i>Plos Neglected Tropical Diseases</i> https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0002249 4) Woolsey I.D., Miller (2021) <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato and Echinococcus multilocularis: a review</i>. <i>Research in Veterinary Science</i> 135:517-522 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2020.11.010 5) Trachsel, D., Deplazes, P., & Mathis, A. (2007). Identification of taeniid eggs in the faeces from carnivores based on multiplex PCR using targets in mitochondrial DNA. <i>Parasitology</i>, 134(6), 911-920. 6) https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/echinococcosis 7) http://atlas.ecdc.europa.eu/public/index.aspx?Dataset=27&HealthTopic=18 8) Eckert, J., Gemmell, M. A., Meslin, F. X., Pawlowski, Z. S., & World Health Organization. (2001). WHO/OIE manual on echinococcosis in humans and animals: a public health problem of global concern. World Organisation for Animal Health.

